

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Most of the scientists (at least in the Northern hemisphere!) are currently on holiday. We thus decided to make reading J.UCS not too strenuous for you, this time around, and just offer you two nice papers. Happy reading!

However, note that this fall J.UCS is already celebrating four continuous years of publications: this must be a record in electronic journals, so please don't forget to submit papers for the "aniversary issues" this fall.

All the best,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu